

ASTEROSEISMOLOGY OF RED GIANT WITH SOLAR-LIKE OSCILLATIONS

Oyirwoth Patrick Abedigamba

Physics Department, Kyambogo University

SSAA Summer School, 26th September 2022

Outline

- Evolution of stars - HR diagram
- Problem statement: On-going open problem
- Solar like oscillations
- Ways of studying solar-like oscillations
- *Kepler* mission & data reduction
- Interesting results
- Conclusion

One minute

What are the states of matter?

Evolution of stars – HR Diagram

Right diagram taken from Christensen – Dalsgaard (2003)

Research Problem

- Red Giants are expected to lose mass on the RGB, nearly all of it at the tip of RGB.
- The amount of mass loss is a major unresolved problem.
- The mass from **asteroseismology** can try to answer this question.

One minute

Why do we study mass loss? Or what is the importance of studying mass loss?

Two minutes

- What is the name of the star at the centre of the solar system?
- What are the mechanisms by which heat/energy is transferred in matter/atmosphere?

Solar-like Oscillations

Christensen – Dalsgaard (2003)

- Outer - surface convection zone
- Turbulent convection (random motion)
- Acoustic noise, sound waves & broad range of frequencies
- Some of the frequencies are resonant inside the spherical cavity of a star and they set up global standing waves

Solar-like oscillations

- The waves are seen as broad envelope of the power spectrum with a peak situated at **maximum freq ν_{\max}**
- Figures on the right -bottom taken from Christensen-Dalsgaard (2003)

Setting the range in frequencies

Christensen-Dalsgaard (2003)

How do we study oscillations?

To study oscillations, one needs to go to fourier space either in time series observations where you measure luminosity changes with time OR

Spectroscopy: where you measure radial velocity changes and finally you take the fourier transform and get a periodogram (power spectrum).

Thanks to the different space missions which have been observing luminosity (brightness) changes with time for many many stars

Example: Kepler Mission

- Successfully launched in March 2009.
- Been observing object within 105 – square degrees in the direction of Cygnus and Lyra.
- Has observed over 150,000 stars.

How to download data for stars?

- You download the data from the publicly available website archive.stsci.edu/pub/kepler/lightcurve.
- The original data is the form of image file (fits files)
- Convert the fits file to readable files.
- Readable file consists of five columns; 1st: Barycentric Julian Date, 2nd: The raw count, 3rd: error in the raw count, 4th: corrected count, 5th: error in the corrected count.

Studying the stars

- Convert the raw count to brightness measure (magnitude) in the form of raw signal and corrected signal.
- The problem is that the data (signal) had drifts and jumps. So, we had to correct for the drifts and jumps.

Periodograms

Need to smooth the data

Global oscillation properties

ν_{\max} (mass & luminosity)
 $\Delta\nu = 0.266\nu^{0.761}$ ($\nu = \nu_{\max}$)

- $\Delta\nu$ (mean density)
- $\delta\nu$ (age)

Top figure: Christensen-Dalsgaard (2003)

Global oscillation properties

Top figure: Christensen-Dalsgaard (2003)

ν_{\max} (mass & luminosity)
 $\Delta\nu = 0.266\nu^{0.761}$ ($\nu = \nu_{\max}$)

- $\Delta\nu$ (mean density)
- $\delta\nu$ (age)
- Asymptotic relation

$$\nu_{n\ell} \approx \Delta\nu\left(n + \frac{1}{2}\ell + \epsilon\right) - \ell(\ell + 1)D_0$$

where $\Delta\nu = \nu_{n\ell} - \nu_{n-1,\ell}$ is the large frequency separation.

Échelle Diagram

- Useful in identifying the harmonic degrees (l values)
- Can help us to understand if a star is moving up a red giant branch or is already in the red clump burning helium. You can see this, why? Because the core are different

Bottom figure: Taken from Christensen – Dalsgaard (2003)

Obtaining Échelle Diagram for the stars in our study

Asymptotic relation for g modes

The problem calls for
Asymptotic relation for g
modes

- Asymptotic relation for g modes say that they are approximately equal spaced in period
- While that of p modes say that they are approximately equal spaced in frequency

Figure taken from Christensen – Dalsgaard (2003)

How to calculate the period spacing for g mode

- (a). Convert the observed frequencies of $l = 1$ to period (s)
- (b). Sort the period in either ascending or descending order
- (c). Calculate the differences in the period, call it ΔP (s)
- (d). Obtain the median of ΔP (s)
- (e). Compare the calculated median period separation with what is known in the literature, i.e., For RGB stars median $\Delta P \approx 50$ s while that of RGC $\Delta P \approx 100 - 300$ s

Period distribution

P (s)	ΔP (s)			
12020	1092.43	1.01	4.6647	83.1947
11934.07	85.93	0.96	5.2637	83.7937
11830.28	103.79	0.9	5.9989	84.5289
10991.12	839.16	1.2	4.5995	90.9825
10906.37	84.75	1.88	5.3065	91.6895
10806.35	100.02	1.04	6.1552	92.5382
10675.93	130.42	0.55	7.2857	93.6687
10244.16	431.77	0.93	3.3806	97.6166
10110.64	133.52	1.05	4.6697	98.9057
10024.54	86.1	1.84	5.5192	99.7552
9925.6	98.94	0.87	6.5136	100.7496
9378.51	547.09	1.47	4.5377	106.6267
9295.4	83.11	1.4	5.4911	107.5801
9192.68	102.72	0.96	6.6932	108.7822
8761.11	431.57	0.59	4.1988	114.1408
8667.98	93.13	0.75	5.4251	115.3671
8082.49	585.49	0.48	5.9293	123.7243

One minute

You have numbers 1, 3, 5, 2 and 4. What is the median?

Sorted Periods Separations

P (s) ΔP (s)

12020	1092.43	1.01	4.6647	83.1947
10991.12	839.16	1.2	4.5995	90.9825
8082.49	585.49	0.48	5.9293	123.7243
9378.51	547.09	1.47	4.5377	106.6267
10244.16	431.77	0.93	3.3806	97.6166
8761.11	431.57	0.59	4.1988	114.1408
10110.64	133.52	1.05	4.6697	98.9057
10675.93	130.42	0.55	7.2857	93.6687
11830.28	103.79	0.9	5.9989	84.5289
9192.68	102.72	0.96	6.6932	108.7822
10806.35	100.02	1.04	6.1552	92.5382
9925.6	98.94	0.87	6.5136	100.7496
8667.98	93.13	0.75	5.4251	115.3671
10024.54	86.1	1.84	5.5192	99.7552
11934.07	85.93	0.96	5.2637	83.7937
10906.37	84.75	1.88	5.3065	91.6895
9295.4	83.11	1.4	5.4911	107.5801

ΔP (s)

11830.28	103.79	0.9	5.9989	84.5289
9192.68	102.72	0.96	6.6932	108.7822
10806.35	100.02	1.04	6.1552	92.5382
9925.6	98.94	0.87	6.5136	100.7496
8667.98	93.13	0.75	5.4251	115.3671
10024.54	86.1	1.84	5.5192	99.7552
11934.07	85.93	0.96	5.2637	83.7937
10906.37	84.75	1.88	5.3065	91.6895
9295.4	83.11	1.4	5.4911	107.5801

Results

OUR RESULTS

- KIC 4902641:

$$\Delta P = 93.1 \text{ s,}$$

$$\Delta \nu = 7.9 \text{ } \mu\text{Hz}$$

- KIC 6928997

$$\Delta P = 58.0 \text{ s,}$$

$$\Delta \nu = 10.0 \text{ } \mu\text{Hz}$$

- KIC 6779699

$$\Delta P = 59.6 \text{ s,}$$

$$\Delta \nu = 8.0 \text{ } \mu\text{Hz}$$

PREVIOUS RESULTS

- KIC 4902641:

$$\Delta P = 96.0 \text{ s,}$$

$$\Delta \nu = 7.9 \text{ } \mu\text{Hz}$$

- KIC 6928997

$$\Delta P = 54.0 \text{ s,}$$

$$\Delta \nu = 10.0 \text{ } \mu\text{Hz}$$

- KIC 6779699

$$\Delta P = 53.0 \text{ s,}$$

$$\Delta \nu = 8.0 \text{ } \mu\text{Hz}$$

Are the stars in red giant branch or are already in the red clump?

Bedding et al. (2011)

Mass from Asteroseismology

$$\nu_{\max} \approx \nu_{\max\odot} \frac{M/M_{\odot}}{(R/R_{\odot})^2 \sqrt{T_{\text{eff}}/T_{\text{eff}\odot}}},$$

$$\log M/M_{\odot} = -7.6056 + \frac{3}{2} \log T_{\text{eff}} + 3 \log \nu_{\max} - 4 \log \Delta\nu,$$

$$\log R/R_{\odot} = -1.1151 + \frac{1}{2} \log T_{\text{eff}} + \log \nu_{\max} - 2 \log \Delta\nu,$$

$$\Delta\nu \approx \Delta\nu_{\odot} \sqrt{\frac{M/M_{\odot}}{(R/R_{\odot})^3}},$$

$$\log L/L_{\odot} = -17.274 + 5 \log T_{\text{eff}} + 2 \log \nu_{\max} - 4 \log \Delta\nu.$$

Mass loss – HR Analysis

Results: Mass loss

Age (Gyr)	Z	Y	Mass loss (%) without correction	Mass loss (%) with correction
2.5	0.017	0.30	5.0±3.2	-2.7±3.3
2.5	0.020	0.30	4.8±3.0	-2.7±3.2
1.9	0.017	0.30	5.3±3.2	-2.2±3.3

Age (Gyr)	Ratio of observed mass to mass from the isochrone
1.9	0.9467 ± 0.0318
2.0	0.9466 ± 0.0318
2.1	0.9473 ± 0.0319
2.4	0.9479 ± 0.0318
2.5	0.9497 ± 0.0317

$$\chi^2 = \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{(t_i - T)^2}{2\sigma_t^2} + \frac{(l_i - L)^2}{2\sigma_l^2} + \frac{(m_i - M)^2}{2\sigma_m^2} \right).$$

Age (Gyr)	Ratio of observed mass to mass from the isochrone
1.9	1.0217±0.0334
2.0	1.0220±0.0335
2.1	1.0227±0.0335
2.4	1.0241±0.0336
2.5	1.0266±0.0326

Conclusion

- Thus we have found a fractional mass loss of $5 \pm 3 \%$ if we assume that no correction to Δv between RC is required
- No mass loss is obtained when a correction of 1.9% in Δv is applied to RC as suggested by models

One minute

Why study open clusters?

Search for red clump stars in the field of NGC 6866

Table 7. Stars with solar-line oscillations in the field of NGC 6866. The columns are the same as in Table 1. The luminosity calculated from the solar-like oscillations, $(\log L/L_{\odot})_v$, the frequency of maximum amplitude, ν_{\max} , and the large separation, $\Delta\nu$, are shown in the last three columns.

KIC	Mem	JJ	Dis	RA	Dec.	Cad	Kp	$\log(T_{\text{eff}})$	KIC $\log L/L_{\odot}$	Solar $(\log L/L_{\odot})_v$	ν_{\max} (μHz)	$\Delta\nu$ (μHz)
8196817	M		9.99	20:03:12	44:03:04	L	12.681	3.6753	1.0912	1.0293	152.8	12.89
8196870			9.25	20:03:15	44:03:40	L	13.674				28.5	3.18
8197162			6.63	20:03:32	44:04:18	L	15.105	3.6348	2.2597		29.8	
8197719			4.99	20:04:06	44:04:55	L	9.872	3.6954		1.4959	97.5	8.34
8197895			6.30	20:04:18	44:04:44	L	15.047	3.6640	1.8949	1.5280	23.6	3.68
8263801			8.11	20:03:11	44:07:36	L	12.115	3.6889	1.8190	1.7630	55.8	5.31
8263826			8.25	20:03:12	44:06:34	L	14.843	3.6601	2.1473	1.4505	35.7	4.68
8264001			5.91	20:03:23	44:10:57	L	13.006	3.5987		1.4924	25.1	3.21
8264006	M	2	5.70	20:03:24	44:10:47	L	11.652	3.6754	1.8314	1.5993	23.6	3.65
8264074	M		5.03	20:03:28	44:10:52	L	13.037	3.6841	1.2238	1.0509	171.9	13.85
8264079	M		4.66	20:03:29	44:09:42	L	12.018	3.7068	1.4401	1.2118	189.5	14.15
8264345			2.75	20:03:44	44:11:25	L	15.363	3.6209	2.2324	1.4659	31.3	3.88
8264410			2.82	20:03:47	44:11:56	L	14.293	3.6608	2.1723	1.5709	27.5	3.84
8264847			3.46	20:04:13	44:08:15	L	14.686	3.6589	1.9536	1.2163	29.0	4.81
8329743			9.95	20:03:12	44:15:48	L	12.210	3.6787	1.6526	1.6553	59.6	5.67
8329820			7.11	20:03:18	44:12:04	L	13.727	3.7073	1.5046	1.2203	186.8	14.00
8329822			9.30	20:03:18	44:16:02	L	15.737	3.6226	2.2484	2.2949	30.8	2.40
8329894	M	1	8.54	20:03:23	44:15:50	L	11.283	3.7169	1.7325	1.8125	82.7	6.81
8330143		17	7.16	20:03:38	44:15:59	L	14.521	3.6290	2.2775	1.2127	58.1	6.26
8330245			5.73	20:03:45	44:14:57	L	14.466	3.5691	2.4719	1.4394	14.5	2.31
8330431			3.61	20:03:57	44:13:06	L	15.443	3.6188	2.2868	2.8122	25.7	1.61
8330620			5.62	20:04:07	44:14:42	L	14.915	3.5923	2.3768	1.6329	17.4	2.42
8330661			3.93	20:04:10	44:12:22	L	12.671	3.6781	1.6333	1.6282	48.2	5.17

- The Kepler mission has been useful in the study of solar-like oscillations in red giant stars
- Why search for red clump stars in this field?
 - (a) Hekker et al (2011) says there are no red giants
 - (b) Balona et al (2013) found that there are 23 red giants

Helium Burning star KIC 8263801 in the field of NGC 6866

THANK YOU

ANY QUESTION ??